

CYCLIC ACETONEMIC VOMITING SYNDROME IN CHILDREN. CLINICAL PRESENTATION OF A CASE OF A CHILD WITH CAVS

Kahtan A.A.

*Dr., MD. Multi-profile hospital for active treatment
"Uni Hospital" – Panagyurishte, Bulgaria*

Abstract

Cyclic acetonemic vomiting syndrome (CAVS) or cyclic vomiting syndrome (CVS) is symptomatic vomiting with a tendency to recurrence, without a clear organic cause. The intervals between individual bouts of vomiting are very different - weeks to years. Continuous vomiting is accompanied by acetonemia and acetonuria. It occurs mainly in early childhood and early school age, especially in sensitive and neuropathic children, but cases of occurrence in infants and the elderly have been described. The etiopathogenesis is largely unknown, but it is likely to be multifactorial. Prodromal signs are headache and severe loss of appetite, which precede vomiting. Severe abdominal pain and seizures are also possible, which can dramatically complicate the clinical picture. The most common complication of CAVS is dehydration. The diagnosis of CAVS involves the exclusion of other conditions that cause similar symptoms, through a detailed history of the current and past illnesses, family history, physical examination and additional tests, which are the cornerstones for making a correct diagnosis. We present a clinical case, which is in line with the literature, of a 9-year-old girl, from the age of 3 until now with repeated episodes of nausea and vomiting, always accompanied by headache, loss of appetite and abdominal pain, several times a year, managed with intravenous infusions of glucose-salt solutions and antiemetic medications in a hospital setting.

Keywords: vomiting, antiemetics, cyclic acetonemic vomiting syndrome, differential diagnosis.

Abbreviation used:

- PPI – Proton pump inhibitor
- Bp – Blood pressure
- RS – Respiratory system
- CS – Cardiovascular system
- RHB – Rhythmic heartbeat
- NS – Nervous system
- MSS – Musculoskeletal system
- HSM – hepatosplenomegaly
- US – Ultrasound
- CRT – Capillary refill time
- GI - Gastrointestinal
- Oas - Organic acidemias
- IEMs – Inborn errors of metabolism
- BGA – blood gas analysis
- BUN – Blood urea nitrogen
- ED – Emergency department
- ORT – Oral rehydration therapy
- IV - Intra venous.

Introduction.

Cyclic acetonemic vomiting syndrome involves recurrent, unexplained episodes of severe nausea and vomiting. Episodes can last from a few hours to a few days. Persistent vomiting can disrupt daily life in both children and adults, requiring children to miss school and adults to miss work. The symptoms, time of day, frequency, severity, and duration of each episode are usually the same for each individual. However, these factors can vary from person to person. CAVS is more common in children than in adults. In most cases, episodes in children begin between the ages of 3 and 7 years. Usually, vomiting is followed by rapid onset of hypochloremic, hypokalemic alkalosis, which must be corrected immediately. But in some cases, episodes of vomiting can exceed 40 times a day, severe metabolic ketoacidosis quickly occurs, which is manifested by acetone breath („apple“ breath), as severe vomiting leads to dehydration, starvation, and decreased carbohydrate

intake, causing the body to produce ketone bodies (beta-hydroxybutyrate), which accumulate in the blood and cause metabolic acidosis with a high anion gap. Although extensive and invasive investigations should be avoided, a baseline investigation to identify organic causes is recommended in all children with CAVS. Management of CAVS requires individualized therapy. Treatment of the acute phase is primarily based on supportive and symptomatic care. [1][2,7,16]

CASE DESCRIPTION.

A 9-year-old girl was admitted to the pediatric ward. She was admitted with a history of repeated vomiting from the previous day, accompanied by nausea, headache, abdominal pain, fatigue and loss of appetite, preceded by pallor, sweating and lethargy. Since the age of 3, she has had repeated similar episodes of nausea and vomiting, accompanied by abdominal pain and headache, several times a year, without a clear cause and without a history of comorbidities. Regularly immunized with good tolerance to vaccines.

The physical examination of the child at the time of admission: A child of apparent age, corresponding to the actual one, with normal physical and neuropsychological development for her age. She was admitted in an unwell general condition, intoxicated, adynamic, without fever. Skin – pale, with reduced turgor, CRT- 3 seconds, without cyanosis and rash units. Acetone breath from the mouth, dry tongue, with white coating. Eyes – sunken. Throat – calm. RS: Nose – patency, symmetrical chest, clear percussion sound, both halves of the chest participate equally in breathing, there are no dyspnea and retractions, vesicular breathing without wheezing or crackles. CS: RHB with a normal frequency for age and clear tones. Blood pressure 85/60 mmHg. Abdomen: soft-elastic walls, allowing deep palpation, with palpatory soreness around the navel and in the epigastrium, normal bowel sounds, without HSM. MSS – normal. NS – without signs of meningo-radicular irritation.

Clinical course of the disease. She was admitted to the pediatric ward with dyspeptic symptoms from the previous day. After three days of treatment with glucose-saline solutions, an PPI and antiemetic drugs, she was discharged in good general condition, normal BP, without fever, without dyspeptic manifestations, without clinical and paraclinical evidence of dehydration and, recommendations to avoid stressful situations and fasting, to observe hygiene and a dietary regimen – excluding trigger foods from the menu, such as chocolate, nuts, citrus fruits, spices, carbonated, energy and alcoholic drinks, etc. Controlled studies showed a reverse dynamics of blood count parameters and normalization of blood sugar. No complications were observed during the hospital stay, except for moderate dehydration at the time of admission for hospital treatment. Acute surgical abdomen, urinary tract abnormalities and acute inflammatory diseases of the abdominal organs were excluded. Basic blood tests and abdominal ultrasound were performed. Upper endoscopy and contrast radiography of the gastrointestinal tract were not indicated. Based on the medical history, physical examination and results of the performed laboratory tests and US, a definitive diagnosis of CAVS was made.

Paraclinical studies: Laboratory data: BGA – normal. WBC – **16.56** g/l; RBC (Ery) – 4.57 T/l; HGB – 128.0 g/l; HCT – 0.415; MCV – 82.9; MCH – 28.0 pg; MCHC – 338.0 g/l; PLT (Thr) – 248.0 g/l; RDW-SD – 37.2; RDW-CV – 12.2; PDW – 12.5; MPV – 10.7; PCT – 0.27; NEUT% - **85.9**; LYM% - 9.3; MONO % - 4.4; EO % - 0.2; BASO % - 0.2; Total bilirubin – 8.6 mmol/l; Direct bilirubin – 1.8 μmol/l; Creatinine (CREA) – serum – 48.7 μmol/l; Urea – 4.9 mmol/l; Total protein – 66.0 g/l; CRP – 0.2 mg/l (normal range – less than 5 mg/l); Na – 136.0 mmol/l; K – 3.8 mmol/l; Cl – 104.0 mmol/l; iCa – 1.19 mmol/l; **Glu – 3.0 mmol/l**; Lact – 1.0 mmol/l; AST – 23.0; ALT – 14.0; GGT – 9.0; Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) – 153.0 U/L; Potassium – 3.8 mmol/l; Sodium – 136 mmol/l; Urinalysis : pH – 6.0; Specific gravity – 1.030; Protein – 0.0; Glucose - Negative; Ketones – **positive (2+)**; Bilirubin – 0.0; Urobilinogen – Normal; Leucocytes – 0.0; Blood – 0.0; Nitrites – Neg; Vitamin C – 0.0; Urine sediment – 3-4 leu/HPF. Control laboratory tests: Glucose (GLUC) – serum – 4.19 mmol/l. WBC – 5.69 g/l; NEUT% - 52.8; LYM% - 33.9; MONO % - 10.7; EO % - 2.1; BASO % - 0.5. Urine analysis: pH – 5.5; Relative specific gravity of urine- 1.020; Protein – 0.0;

Glucose – 0.0; Ketones – 0.0; Billirubin – 0.0 Urobilinogen – Not increased; Leucocytes – 0.0; Blood – 0.0; Nytrites – Neg; Urine-sediment – 2-3 leucocytes/HPF. Instrumental examinations: US – without ultrasound data for pathological changes in the abdominal organs.

Treatment provided, includes: Metoclopramide hydrochloride, 10 (sol.inj.5mg/ml 2 ml x 1) – 1 x amp 10 mg i.v. for day one; Famotidine, 20 (powd.inj.20mg+solv.5ml x 1) – 2 x 20 mg i.v. for 3 days; Ringer Braun sol.inf.500ml – i.v. once daily for 2 days; Serum glucosae Braun, 500 (sol.inf.500ml x 1) – once daily for 3 days.

Discussion of literature data.

CVS is characterized by stereotypical episodes of paroxysmal vomiting and nausea with a return to baseline health between episodes ^[1,2,6,7]. Hypoglycemia is always present in the initial phase. ^[1] This distinctive on-off temporal pattern characterized by four phases is essential for diagnosis ^[2,7,16]. Up to 75% of children exhibit symptoms during the night or early in the morning (generally 2.00–7.00 a.m.), ^[10,17,18], lasting several hours to days, although rarely >72 h ^[2]. Four phases have been identified: prodromal; emetic; recovery, and inter-episodic ^[16]. About 90% of patients experience a prodromal phase ^[16], that is characterized mainly by signs and symptoms of autonomic dysfunction such as pallor, sweating and lethargy ^[10,18]. It generally occurs a few hours before the vomit onset and is similar to that of migraine headache attack^[26]. The emetic phase is characterized by a projectile, intense vomit, often leading to significant dehydration. Vomiting is often bilious and associated to other gastrointestinal symptoms, such as abdominal pain, which is described in up to 80% of children, anorexia, nausea and diarrhea ^{[2][21]}. Abdominal pain is described in the prodromal as well as in the other phases ^[19]. Emotional stress (generally of an excitatory nature) and infections are the most common triggers. Certain foods (e.g., chocolate, cheese, and caffeine), fasting, fever, lack of sleep, allergies, dietary and menstruation are also common trigger factors ^[9,15,20]. There are two main different sets of criteria to consider for diagnosis of CAVS in children: The NASPGHAN ^[1], and the Rome IV^[6,7] classifications (Table 1). NASPGHAN guideline recommend a minimum of five attacks of intense nausea and vomiting for the diagnosis in children ^[2,5], while a minimum of two episodes are required in Rome IV criteria ^[6,7].

Current classification for the diagnosis of pediatric Cyclic Vomiting Syndrome (CVS).

NASPGHAN

All of the criteria must be met

1. At least five attacks in any interval or a minimum of three attacks during a 6-months Period
2. Episodic attacks of intense nausea and vomiting lasting 1 h to 10 days and occurring at least 1 week apart
3. Stereotypical pattern and symptoms in the individual patient
4. Vomiting during attacks occurs at least 4 times/h for at least 1 h
5. Return to baseline health between episodes
6. Not attributed to another disorder

ROME IV**Children and Adolescents**

Must include all of the following

1. The occurrence of 2 or more periods of intense, unremitting nausea and paroxysmal vomiting, lasting hours to days within a 6-months period
2. Episodes are stereotypical in each patient
3. Episodes are separated by weeks to months with return to baseline health between episodes
4. After appropriate medical evaluation, the symptoms cannot be attributed to another condition

NEONATES AND TODDLERS

Must include all of the following

1. Two or more periods of unremitting paroxysmal vomiting with or without retching, lasting hours to days within a 6-months period
2. Episodes are stereotypical in each patient
3. Episodes are separated by weeks to months with return to baseline health between episodes of vomiting.

Diagnosis and differential Diagnosis.

The key to diagnosing CAVS is a detailed physical examination, current and past medical history, so that extensive and invasive testing can be avoided. Diagnosing CVS efficiently and cost-effectively can be achieved by early clinical recognition based upon clinical criteria (Table 1). The emergency physician should use a systematic approach that has to be age and developmentally appropriate to be able to identify life-threatening emergencies, such as bowel obstruction, diabetic ketoacidosis, adrenal crisis, toxic ingestion, or increased intracranial pressure [32]. An upper GI endoscopy may be required if patients experience chronic gastrointestinal symptoms or large amounts of hematemesis. While ketonuria should always be considered abnormal in neonates, it is a physiological result of catabolism in late infancy, childhood, and even adolescence. However, hyperketosis >6 mmol/l of total plasma ketone bodies that cause metabolic acidosis (serum bicarbonate <18 mmol/l) is always pathological. Ketosis in absence of other biochemical abnormalities such as acidosis, hyperlactatemia, or hypoglycemia, rarely is due to an IEMs and is likely to be a normal

physiological response to fasting, catabolism, vomiting, medium-chain triglyceride enriched or other ketogenic diets. Conversely, ketoacidosis with or without hypoglycemia could be seen in several metabolic disorders, especially Oas. Children who present in ED with a CVS diagnosis (Rome IV criteria) and without any additional warning symptoms require only a limited set of further investigation. During each episode, laboratory testing should be performed, consisting of electrolytes, glucose, BUN, creatinine, and urinalysis to primary monitor for acute hypovolemia and electrolyte disturbances. It is clear, e.g., that mild metabolic acidosis, hypoglycemia, and ketosis are consistent with CVS while severe acidosis or hypoglycemia (in particular non-ketotic hypoglycemia) warrant further evaluation for an inborn error of metabolism, especially in infants and toddlers. It is also important to identify triggers (in particular infections), and recognize comorbid [33].

The basis of differential diagnosis is a review of systems, which should look for symptoms of causal disorders:

- Vomiting that has occurred in the past and is episodic, short-lived, and has no other accompanying

symptoms suggests CVS. While CVS is characterized by stereotypical episodes with prodromal symptoms such as nausea, abdominal pain, anorexia and pallor, emesis in brain tumor or other intracranial masses occur without prodromal symptoms and is triggered by a rapid change in body position and nausea is rarely present.

- Delayed passage of meconium, later onset of vomiting, or both may indicate Hirschsprung disease or intestinal stenosis. An infant or young child with colicky abdominal pain, signs of intermittent pain or listlessness, and absent or bloody stools needs to be evaluated for an intussusception. Any neonate or infant with recurrent or bilious (yellow or green) emesis or projectile vomiting most likely has a gastrointestinal obstruction and probably requires surgical intervention. A child or adolescent with fever and abdominal pain followed by vomiting, anorexia, and decreased bowel sounds should be evaluated for appendicitis.

- Galactosemia, Hereditary Fructose Intolerance (HFI) and Tyrosinaemia type I, are the main conditions in this category characterized by vomiting plus acute liver failure, requiring immediate and specific treatment. Patients may show acute deterioration, vomiting, seizures, dehydration, hypoglycaemia, liver failure and tubulopathy.

- Specifically, renal colic and/or pelvic-ureteric junction obstruction may cause recurrent vomiting of urologic origin with possible symptom-free interval periods.

- Also, recurrent infections, particularly enteritis, hepatitis, otitis media and chronic sinusitis may manifest with vomiting. [8] [28][29]

Treatment.

The management of CVS requires an individually tailored therapy that takes into consideration the frequency and severity of attacks, and resultant disability balanced against the potential side effects of treatment. The two key treatment arms are prophylactic measures and medications administered in the interictal period and acute and supportive interventions given during attacks [1] [2]. Treatment of CAVS includes:

1. Management of dehydration with IV rehydration with glucose-salt solutions and correction of electrolyte and disturbances in the acid-base balance of the blood.

2. Useful drugs available for pharmacological treatment, include:

- **Famotidine.** It has no direct antiemetic effect, but is a competitive inhibitor of histamine (H₂) receptors associated with the parietal cells of the stomach, so reduces the amount of acid produced by the stomach, and is generally well tolerated with few side effects. Administered at a dose of 0.5 - 1 mg/kg/dose (max 20 mg/dose) every 12 hours IV.

- **Omeprazole.** It is a proton-pump inhibitor used to reduce the amount of acid produced by the stomach. So Omeprazole may have an antiemetic effect, meaning it can help reduce nausea and vomiting, especially when the symptoms are related to gastrointestinal issues. Administered at a dose of 0.5 - 1 mg/kg/dose (max 40 mg/dose) every 12 hrs IV.

- **Metoclopramide.** It is a dopamine receptor antagonist that acts both centrally and peripherally by increasing gastric motility and decreasing afferent impulses to the chemoreceptor trigger zone. Drowsiness, dizziness, agitation, headache, diarrhea, akathisia, and dystonia are the most common adverse effects. 0.1 mg/kg orally or IV every 6 hours (maximum 10 mg/dose)

- **Diphenhydramine.** It is a H₁- antagonist and has antiemetic, sedative and antihistamine effects. Прилага се в доза 1 -1.25 mg/kg/dose every 6 hrs IV.

- **Ondansetron.** It is a selective serotonin (5-HT₃) receptor blocker that inhibits the initiation of the vomiting reflex in the periphery [15]. It can be used at a dose of 0.15 mg/kg per dose IV, oral/sublingual every 8 hrs (max dose 8 mg) or, if the oral form is used, for children 2 to 4 years, 2 mg every 8 hours; for those 4 to 11 years, 4 mg every 8 hours; for those ≥ 12 years, 8 mg every 8 hours. A single dose of ondansetron is safe and effective in children who have acute gastroenteritis and are unable to tolerate ORT. By facilitating ORT, this drug may prevent the need for IV fluids or, in children given IV fluids, may help prevent hospitalization. Typically, only a single dose is used because repeated doses can cause persistent diarrhea. Other common adverse effects include headache, dizziness, drowsiness, blurred vision, constipation, muscle stiffness, tachycardia, and hallucinations [9]. Moreover, since QT prolongation can occur with the administration of this medication, a baseline ECG is recommended. When ondansetron fails to control nausea and vomiting, sleep induced by sedatives may be the only way to provide symptomatic relief. The most effective combination is ondansetron and lorazepam (0.05–0.1 mg/kg/dose IV every 6 h). Alternatively, chlorpromazine (0.5–1 mg/kg/dose every 6 h) and diphenhydramine (1–1.25 mg/kg/dose every 6 h) can be used together, but this provides less antiemetic and more sedative effect [15].

- **Promethazine** is an H₁ receptor blocker (antihistamine) that inhibits the emetic center response to peripheral stimulants. Promethazine dosage: For children > 2 years, 0.25 to 1 mg/kg (maximum 25 mg) orally, IM, IV, or rectally every 4 to 6 hours. The most common adverse effects are respiratory depression, sedation, dizziness, anxiety, blurred vision, dry mouth, impotence, and constipation; the drug is contraindicated in children < 2 years. Therapeutic doses of promethazine can cause extrapyramidal adverse effects, including torticollis.

Prophylactic Treatment and Lifestyle Changes and Dietary Restrictions.

A careful history and a detailed vomiting diary recording frequency of episodes, type of meal before episodes, and potentially aggravating life events can help to identify and avoid potential triggers in 70% of children [15]. Lifestyle changes include: [2] avoidance of excessive excitement (e.g., birthdays, holidays, and over-exertion); [3] avoidance of trigger foods. Although extensive dietary restriction of potential trigger foods is not recommended, it is reasonable to test eliminating foods or chemical substances that appear to be aggravating factors for migraines (e.g., cheese, chocolate, hot dogs, aspartame, monosodium glutamate and alcohol)

^[36]. Also, children with documented food sensitivities to specific foods (e.g., cow, soy, or egg white proteins) have been shown to improve following specific dietary elimination ^[4,37]. Consumption of high-carbohydrate snacks between meals, before physical exertion, and at bedtime should be used when a patient's history suggests fasting-induced attacks^[15]. During the interictal period, lifestyle changes and the use of reassurance (e.g., attacks are not self-induced) and anticipatory guidance (e.g., improvement with age and knowledge that effective therapies are available) can themselves have a significant therapeutic effect reducing the frequency of attacks ^[35]. In patients with anxiety, cognitive behavioral therapy and biofeedback may be needed ^[34]. The indication for prophylactic pharmacotherapy depends on attack intensity (more than every 1–2 months) and severity (exceeding 2 days or requiring hospitalization), the impairment of the QoL (e.g., frequent school absences) and if attack treatments are ineffective or cause side effects. The choice of prophylactic pharmacological treatment should take into account the age of the child, psychological comorbidities and formulation and safety profile of the drug. The low initial dose is recommended, and increase incrementally, titrating to effect. ^[2] Cyproheptadine is effective in young children with CVS and is the first choice for children 5 years old or younger ^[40–42]. The recommended dose is 0.25–0.5 mg/kg/day divided twice or three times per day. Pizotifen 0.5–1.5 mg at night is an alternative to cyproheptadine with the same side effects. ^[43]

Prognosis. CVS resolves, in most children (50–70%) in late childhood or early adolescence ^[12–14, 25, 26]. Noteworthy, 78% of parents felt that the provision of a positive diagnosis and information made a significant impact on the severity of vomiting ^[13]. According to another study on 28 cases (adult and children) with CVS, 62% of patients showed a gradual improvement in symptoms and 24% had complete resolution after a mean of 7 years ^[30]. Many children with CVS stop having emetic episodes as they grow older. Less commonly, CVS persists in adulthood ^[27].

Conclusion. Since serious metabolic, neurologic and surgical conditions may underlie the clinical picture of recurrent vomiting, it is recommended that all children should undergo baseline testing toward identifying organic causes. In ED setting biochemical, radiographic assessments, and potentially endoscopic/ultrasound assessment should be considered. Biochemical testing should include arterial-blood gas test, complete blood count, serum electrolytes and glucose, liver panel, lipase, BUN, creatinine and urinalysis, also to exclude possible dehydration. Once life-threatening causes are excluded and acute alterations are treated, the patient should be referred to an appropriate pediatric specialist (e.g., gastroenterologist, surgeon, neurologist, metabolic experts), to avoid inappropriate further ED visits and a delay in the diagnosis and preventive therapy in case of CVS. Emotional stress (generally of an excitatory nature) and infections are the most common triggers. Certain foods (e.g., chocolate, cheese, and caffeine), fasting, fever, lack of sleep, allergies, dietary and menstruation are also common trigger factors.

In this regard, the best prevention to reduce the risk of a vomiting episode is to avoid the above-mentioned triggers.

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